

A typical presentation of genital chlamydia

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Abstract:

Chlamydia is one of the most common sexually transmitted infections all over the world.

It is passed on through unprotected sex (sex without a condom) and is particularly common in sexually active teenagers and young adults.

Most people with chlamydia do not notice any symptoms and do not know they have it. Although chlamydia does not usually cause any symptoms and can normally be treated with a short course of antibiotics, it can be serious if it's not treated early if left untreated, the infection can spread to other parts of your body and lead to long-term health problems, such as pelvic inflammatory disease (PID). And infertility. It can also sometimes cause arthritis. Rare complication is perihepatitis (Fitz Hugh Curtis syndrome).our rare case, presented with abdominal discomfort, ascites and elevated CA125, no genitourinary symptoms.

Molecular detection of CFFDNA for early laboratory diagnosis of X linked disorders carriers

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Abstract:

Enhancement of DNA detection assays increase the use of non-invasive prenatal diagnosis that is consequently enhances the supervision plan of pregnant woman with genetic disorder expected babies. Aim of work: Current work was planed to examine plasma of pregnant women starting from 6th week pregnancy for Cell-free fetal DNA, to determine embryonic sex type with consequent prospect of detection of fetal anomalies such as aneuploidies. Method: Samples collected from 6th week till 11th week of pregnancy according to pregnancy age and tested using Real time PCR for determination of fetal sex. Results: Testing of samples resulted in detection of fetal sex starting from 6th week and the later the gestational age the better the result for detection of fetal sex, all results were confirmed by Ultrasound scan and neonatal outcome. Testing results revealed PCR detection for 58 males and 92 females with confusion in one fetus due to non-identical twins.

Key words:

Fetal DNA, Xlinked disorders

Laser acupuncture effect on fetal well-being during induction of labor

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Abstract:

Labor induction with traditional drugs is sometimes associated with fetal complications as fetal distress or death. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of labor induction by laser acupuncture on fetal well-being in postterm pregnancy. Nulliparous women at 40 weeks or greater were randomized to sham laser group versus laser acupuncture group. Each session consisted of laser application on bilateral points LI 4, SP 6, BL 31, and BL 32. The study was conducted in Cairo University, National Institute of Laser Enhanced Sciences. Sixty nulliparous women were randomized into laser acupuncture group n=30 and control group n=30. Women were treated in both groups in three consecutive days in post-date pregnancy. Results (66.6 %) showed a significant difference in rate of normal vaginal delivery (NVD) between acupuncture group (50 %) and control group (50 %) ($p=0.002$). There was no significant difference of enrollment delivery time between laser acupuncture and sham groups ($p>0.05$). There were six cases of cesarean section (CS) due to no fetal movement with normal cardiotocography (CTG). Laser acupuncture has no effect on fetus, and its effect on fetal movement needs more investigations. Laser can induce labor if the cervical length is less than 1 cm and dilation (0).

Keywords:

Laser, Acupuncture, Labor, Induction

Therapeutic ketosis and the broad field of applications for the ketogenic diet: Ketone ester applications & clinical updates

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Abstract:

It has been recently shown that nutritional ketosis is effective against seizure disorders and various acute/chronic neurological disorders. Physiologically, glucose is the primary metabolic fuel for cells. However, many neurodegenerative disorders have been associated with impaired glucose transport/metabolism and with mitochondrial dysfunction, such as Alzheimer's/Parkinson's disease, general seizure disorders, and traumatic brain injury. Ketone bodies and tricarboxylic acid cycle intermediates represent alternative fuels for the brain and can bypass the ratelimiting steps associated with impaired neuronal glucose metabolism. Therefore, therapeutic ketosis can be considered as a metabolic therapy by providing alternative energy substrates. It has been estimated that the brain derives over 60% of its total energy from ketones when glucose availability is limited. In fact, after prolonged periods of fasting or ketogenic diet (KD), the body utilizes energy obtained from free fatty acids (FFAs) released from adipose tissue. Because the brain is unable to derive significant energy from FFAs, hepatic ketogenesis converts FFAs into ketone bodies-hydroxybutyrate (BHB) and acetoacetate (AcAc)-while a percentage of AcAc spontaneously decarboxylates to acetone. Large quantities of ketone bodies accumulate in the blood through this mechanism. This represents a state of normal physiological ketosis and can be therapeutic. Ketone bodies are transported across the blood-brain barrier by monocarboxylic acid transporters to fuel brain function. Starvation or nutritional ketosis is an essential survival mechanism that ensures metabolic flexibility during prolonged fasting or lack of carbohydrate ingestion. Therapeutic ketosis leads to metabolic adaptations that may improve brain metabolism, restore mitochondrial ATP production, decrease reactive oxygen species production, reduce inflammation, and increase neurotrophic factors' function. It has been shown that KD mimics the effects of fasting and the lack of glucose/insulin signaling, promoting a metabolic shift towards fatty acid utilization. In this work, the author reports a number of successful case reports treated through metabolic ketosis.

Figure 1: Ketone Ester significantly increased resistance against

Biography:

Raffaele Pilla, Pharm.D., Ph.D., Doctor Europaeus, received his Master's degree in Pharmacy at G. d'Annunzio University in Chieti-Pescara, Italy in 2005, where he also served internships at the Cell Physiology Laboratory and Molecular Biology Laboratory. Prior, he was an Erasmus Student at Faculté de Pharmacie de Reims in Reims, France. He received his Doctor Europaeus in 2010 from Pitié-Salpêtrière Institute in Paris, France. Also in 2010, he received his Ph.D. in Biochemistry, Physiology, and Pathology of Muscle at G. d'Annunzio University in Chieti-Pescara, Italy. He was hired as a Postdoctoral Scholar in the Department of Pharmacology and Physiology at the University of South Florida in Tampa, on two research grants funded by the Office of Naval Research (US Navy) and Divers' Alert Network. He has written and lectured widely worldwide. He has been involved in ongoing research at the University of South Florida with the use of ketone esters.

Beta-hemolytic streptococcus as a risk factor for the development of preterm birth

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Abstract:

Significance

In modern conditions for the Re-public of Kazakhstan, as well as for other countries, preterm birth (PR) is a pressing is-sue in the field of obstetrics and neonatology. The frequency of PR in the Republic of Ka-zakhstan (2010-2017) does not tend to de-crease and ranges from 6.1% to 7.4% [1]. Based on scientific studies on the problem of PR, there are convincing data indicating the relationship between the presence of an in-fectious agent, and in particular beta-hemolytic streptococcus (BHS) and the onset of PR [2].

Aim and tasks: detecting BHS in PR using rapid test (digital PCR).

Material and methods:

A prospective cohort study of 84 cas-es of preterm birth was conducted. The bio-material was taken from the vaginal area and anorectum. A rapid test (digital PCR) was performed for 84 pregnant women within 1 hour on the BHS. All pregnant women were divided into 3 groups: the first group - 45 pregnant women with a gestation of 22-27 weeks; the second group - 28 pregnant wom-en with a period of 28-33 weeks; the third group - 11 pregnant women at 34-37 weeks. Data processing was performed using SPSS version 18.0. The study of the characteristics of pregnant women was carried out using the PSI questionnaires. Statistical analysis applied the criteria of Pearson, Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Student.

Results:

The average age of the pregnant women of the examined groups had no sig-nificant differences and was 26.6 ± 2.3 years. From the anamnesis, it was found that in 22.6% of cases, BHS was diagnosed be-fore pregnancy. For the first time, BHS dur-ing pregnancy was detected in 77.3% of the pregnant women. The study of social factors showed that 51.6% of pregnant women had labor activity under conditions of chronic stress. The average age of the menarche of the examined groups had no significant dif-ferences and amounted to 12.8 ± 1.5 years. The high frequency of menstrual disorders after the onset of sexual activity in 58.9% of patients draws attention. Analysis of the pari-ty of childbirth showed that the number of primiparous and multiparous among the ex-aminated groups is the same ($46.1 \pm 2.9\%$ and $55.0 \pm 5.0\%$). A screening study of the bio-material from the vaginal area and anorectum on the BHS using digital PCR in puerperas with PR showed a high incidence of BHS 63.1%. At the same time, the frequency of BHS detection in the contents of the vagina was 36.9%, in the content of the anorectum 28.6%, and in 32.1% the BHS was detected in both biomaterials.

Findings:

1. A screening study of the biomaterial from the vaginal area and anorectum on beta-hemolytic streptococcus using digital PCR in puerperas with preterm birth showed a high frequency (63.1%) of detecting BHS;
2. Reliably more often ($p < 0.05$) BHS was diagnosed in group 1 of the study with a pe-riod of 22-27 weeks of pregnancy.

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To analyze the characteristics of disseminated *Penicillium marneffei* (PSM) in children

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Abstract:

Objective: To analyze the characteristics of disseminated *Penicillium marneffei* (PSM) in the context of non-HIV (human immunodeficiency virus).

Methods: Retrospective analysis on the clinical profile, treatment, and outcomes of 15 children with non-HIV disseminative PSM in the past 15 years.

Results: 15 children (male: female = 9:6) had a median age of 23 months and a range of 3 months to 4 years of age. They were often associated with a cough, tachypnea, splenomegaly and lymph nodes enlargement. ESR was elevated by 93.3% (14/15), 80% (8/10) were fungal G tests positive and 87.5% (7/8) fungal GM tests positive. Bone marrow culture and lymph node biopsy showed the highest positive rate of PM.

Conclusion: Non-HIV disseminated PSM in children mostly occurs in infants under 3 years of age, and clinical and laboratory diagnosis lack specificity. Patients with a long course of the disease without timely anti-fungal treatment are associated with death.

Figure 1: A) shows the mycelial phase at 25°C; B shows a typical branchlike branch-ing change; C shows a circular, roundish spore-like appearance in the cytoplasm of the histological cells in a lung biopsy. Amine silver (+), PAS (+), gram (-) tissue changes to lung *Penicillium marneffei*; D picture is lymph node biopsy, round cytoplasmic spheroidoid spore-like, special Staining: acid-fast (-), hexamine-silver (+), Gimsa (+), PAS (+), gram (-), tissue chang-es to lymph node *Penicillium marneffei* in-fec-tion.

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Antenatal steroids-Where are we?

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Abstract:

Early steroids studies in fifties and sixties involved animals and the effects they had upon various organs. It was not until in 1969 when GC Liggins, while studying the effects of steroids upon the initiation of labour in fetal lambs, that he noticed the steroids treated lambs not only had initiation of labour but they also had relatively more mature lungs and better survival.¹ This further led to studies which directly showed the effect of steroids upon maturing lungs by accelerated surfactant appearance. In 1972, landmark study by GC Liggins and RN Howie showed that steroids could reduce the incidence of RDS in preterm neonates.² This study led pathway to numerous studies all over the world showing effects of steroids in maturation of lungs. However, they also showed caution regarding the potential adverse effects. In 1990, systemic review by P Crowley clearly showed the beneficial effects of steroids in reduction of RDS with minimal adverse effects.³ Further in 1994, consensus statement by NIH gave the current recommendation and regimen for antenatal steroids for preterm deliveries.⁴ Further consolidation of the positive effects of steroids was done by meta-analysis by D Roberts in 2000 and further in 2006 and 2017.⁵ However, despite clear evidence of beneficial effects, 2014 study in Lancet showed that the use of corticosteroids in lower income countries like Nepal, Afghanistan, Niger, and Congo was low.⁶ The use of antenatal steroids must be encouraged especially in lower income countries for reducing the neonatal mortality rates in these countries.

Biography:

Dr Bikash Shrestha completed his MBBS degree and MD Paediatrics from Armed Forces Medical College, Pune in 2003 and 2012 respectively. He completed Fellowship in Neonatology from National Neonatology Forum, India in 2015. He is the neonatologist/ paediatrician working in the Department of Paediatrics, Nepalese Army Institute of Health Sciences, Shree Birendra Hospital, Kathmandu, Nepal. He is actively involved in teaching MBBS students and conducting CME conferences for the paediatricians. He has more than 6 publications including a review article, authored a chapter in a book and is involved in various research activities in the field of neonatology and paediatrics.

Compassionate and respectful maternity care during facility based child birth and women's intent to use maternity service in Bahir Dar, Ethiopia, 2018

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Abstract:

Compassionate and respectful maternity care is one of the most important facilitating factors to increase access to skilled maternity care. Disrespect and abuse is a violation of human rights and is the main hindering factor preventing skilled birth utilization versus other more commonly recognized deterrents such as financial and geographical obstacles. The main objective of this study was to assess compassionate and respectful maternity care during facility based child birth and women's intent to use maternity service in Bahir Dar, Ethiopia. A community based cross-sectional study design triangulated with in-depth interview was conducted to collect data from study participants in Bahir Dar town from March 1-March 30/2017. Study subjects were selected through systematic random sampling based on their proportional distribution of sample size to each sub-city. Structured questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data and semi-structured guide for in-depth interview. The data was coded and entered into Epi data 3.1 version and the analysis was carried out in statistical package for social science 22 versions. Univariate, Bivariate and multivariate analysis with 95 % CI was carried out. From the total of 422 mothers interviewed 410 responded for the question with a response rate of (97.2%). The overall prevalence of disrespect and abuse was 67.1 % with 95% CI (63-72) .Almost all of the mothers were experienced at list one form of disrespect and abuse. The most prevalent form of abuse and disrespect was physical abuse 236(57.6%) and non- consented care 236(57.6%). Disrespect and abuse is prevalent on low socio economic group, as length of stay in health facility increase disrespect and abuse increase and disrespect and abuse were significantly increase at governmental hospital than private at P- value of less than 0.05. This study showed a high prevalence of disrespect and abuse during facility child birth in Bahir Dar town, Ethiopia as compared to previous literature. Being from rural area, having complications during delivery and mothers who gave birth through caesarian section were more likely to be exposed to disrespect and abuse than other women. Mistreatment of mothers during facility child birth is a health facility failure, a violation of women's rights and a notable barrier for institutional delivery.

Key words:

Compassionate, respectful, disrespect, abuse, child birth, Ethiopia

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Effect of Physiotherapy in pregnancy, labor and postpartum period.

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Abstract:

Pregnancy, labor and childbirth cause a lot of physiological, emotional changes in women. Aches and discomforts developed at these stages when left untreated leaves serious health problems. Physiotherapy during these stages enables women to adjust and cope with the changes. Antenatal Exercises and counseling focuses on prevention and treatment of common co-morbidities of pregnancy such as low back ache, pedal edema, cramping etc. It also aims on postural changes to be adapted, modifying the positions of activities of daily living.

Antenatal Counseling plays a vital role in educating the mother about childbirth which apparently prevents anxiety and stress throughout the gestational period and labor, promoting better pain tolerance especially in primigravida women. Therefore prevents undue energy expenditure during the first stage of labor, ensuring the best utility of energy conserved, in the following stages for the expulsion of foetus and placenta. The low stress and anxiety level enables the mother to focus on the labor and not the parturition pain, thus prevents anxiety induced complications promoting smooth progression of each stage.

Physiotherapy in puerperium aims at educating the mother on lactation enhancement, breast and nipple care, baby handling and best nursing positions. In Postpartum physiotherapy, screening for conditions like diastasis recti, dysphoric milk ejection reflex, urinary and fecal incontinence etc. which women are likely to develop following childbirth, are detected early and treated conservatively with exercises that are modified according to the patient's condition and type of delivery. Hence, this study permits to discuss briefly on, how effectively Physiotherapy could benefit women in pregnancy, labor and postpartum period.

Biography:

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Direct evidence of viral infection and mitochondrial alterations in the brain of fetuses at high risk for schizophrenia

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Abstract:

There is increasing evidences that favor the prenatal beginning of schizophrenia. These evidences point toward intra-uterine environmental factors that act specifically during the second pregnancy trimester producing a direct damage of the brain of the fetus [1]. The current available technology doesn't allow observing what is happening at cellular level since the human brain is not exposed to a direct analysis in that stage of the life in subjects at high risk of developing schizophrenia. Methods. In 1977 we began a direct electron microscopic research of the brain of fetuses at high risk from schizophrenic mothers in order to finding differences at cellular level in relation to controls. Results. In these studies we have observed within the nuclei of neurons the presence of complete and incomplete viral particles that reacted in positive form with antibodies to herpes simplex hominis type I [HSV1] virus, and mitochondria alterations [2]. Conclusion. The importance of these findings can have practical applications in the prevention of the illness keeping in mind its direct relation to the aetiology and physiopathology of schizophrenia. A study of the gametes or the amniotic fluid cells in women at risk of having a schizophrenic offspring is considered. Of being observed the same alterations that those observed previously in the cells of the brain of the studied foetuses, it would intend to these women in risk of having a schizophrenia descendant, previous information of the results, the voluntary medical interruption of the pregnancy or an early anti HSV1 viral treatment as preventive measure of the later development of the illness.

Biography:

Segundo Mesa Castillo. As Specialist in Neurology, he worked for 10 years in the Institute of Neurology of Havana, Cuba. He has worked in Electron Microscopic Studies on Schizophrenia for 32 years. He was awarded with the International Price of the Stanley Foundation Award Program and for the Professional Committee to work as a fellowship position in the Laboratory of the Central Nervous System Studies, National Institute of Neurological Diseases and Stroke under Dr. Joseph Gibbs for a period of 6 months, National Institute of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, Washington D.C. USA, June 5, 1990. At present he is member of the Scientific Board of the Psychiatric Hospital of Havana and give lectures to residents in psychiatry.

Iodine Status during Pregnancy among Tea Garden Workers in Assam and its Effect on the Foetus

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Abstract:

Iodine Status during Pregnancy among Tea Garden Workers in Assam and its Effect on the Foetus Dutta HK1* and Baruah M2 1 Associate Professor, Department of Pediatric Surgery, Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh, India 2 Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh, Assam, India

Abstract Iodine deficiency during pregnancy causes wide spectrum of disorders in the fetus. Tea garden workers in Assam are known to have high prevalence of endemic goiter and congenital malformations. The present study is aimed to evaluate the iodine status of pregnant tea garden workers and its effect on the fetus. Urinary iodine (UI) level in casual urine samples was estimated in each trimester in 156 pregnant and 160 age-matched non-pregnant women from the same community. Although normal UI values were found in all pregnant women, significantly higher values were noted during the second trimester and among the older women. 12 babies were born preterm. Malformations were noted among 16 babies. 2 women in the control group received treatment for hypothyroid status. Normal UI recorded in the study may be because of universal consumption of iodized salt. Factors other than iodine may be responsible for the malformations noted in this study.

Key words:

Iodine nutrition; Pregnancy; Congenital malformations.

The Purpose of Temperature of Fever

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Abstract:

When the disease becomes threat to life or organs blood circulation decreases, Temperature of fever will emerges to increase prevailing blood circulation. And it acts as a protective covering of the body to sustain life.

When blood flow decrease to brain, the patient becomes fainted-delirious .If we try to decreases temperature of fever, the blood circulation will further reduced. Blood circulation never increases without temperature increase. Delirious can never be cured without increase in blood circulation.

The temperature of fever is not a surplus temperature or it is not to be eliminated from the body. During fever, our body temperature increases like a brooding hen`s increased body temperature.

The actual treatment to fever is to increase blood circulation. Two ways to increase blood circulation.

1. Never allow body temperature to lose

2. Apply heat from outside to the body. When the temperature produced by body due to fever and heat which we applied on the body combines together, the blood circulation increases.

Then body will stop to produce heat to increase blood circulation. And body will get extra heat from outside without any usage of energy.

How can we prove that the temperature of fever is to increase blood circulation?

If we ask any type of question related to fever by assuming that the temperature of fever is to increase blood circulation we will get a clear answer. If avoid or evade from this definition we will never get proper answer to even a single question

If we do any type of treatment by assuming that the temperature of fever is to increase blood circulation , the body will accept, at the same time body will resist whatever treatment to decrease blood circulation.

No further evidence is required to prove the temperature of fever is to increase blood circulation.

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Biography:

A practicing physician in the field of healthcare in the state of Kerala in India for the last 30 years and very much interested in basic research. My interest is spread across the fever , inflammation and back pain,. I am a writer. I already printed and published nine books in these subjects. I wrote hundreds of articles in various magazines.

After scientific studies we have developed 8000 affirmative cross checking questions. It can explain all queries related with fever.